

The Influence of Use of Google Classroom Media on Indonesian Language Learning Outcomes of Class XI Students Of SMKN 2 Sidrap

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ABSTRACT

This research uses a quantitative approach method and a type of experimental research which aims to test the influence of Google Classroom media on Indonesian language learning outcomes for class XI SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng Rappang. The population in this study was all class There are 2 variables in this study, namely the independent variable, the influence of Google Classroom media (x), while the dependent variable is the results of learning Indonesian in class XI (y). This research was carried out in class XI of SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap. Data collection techniques use documentation and tests. The test result data that has been collected is then analyzed using the t-test formula. Based on the results of data analysis, the experimental group score = 85.067 and the control group score = 77.714 and in the t.test the Tcount was 2.833 > from Ttable 5% (2.052) with db 27. Based on the research results it can be concluded that the use of Google Classroom media has an impact on Indonesian language learning results for class XI students at SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a planned effort that aims to improve the quality and develop the potential of every human being. That matter in line with Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which states that: education has an important role in the progress of a nation. Education must be able to accommodate learning activities so that later have ability in face change era. Learning an activity concept in which there is a teaching and learning process with demands that students master a number of learning (Wafiqni, et al., 2018).

Education is learning For produce quality according to the objectives and regulated by Law of the Republic of Indonesia number 20 of the year 2003 About System Education National, "education is business aware And planned For realize atmosphere Study And process learning so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, morals glorious, as well as Skills Which required himself, society, nation And country" (Ministry Law And HAM, 2012).

The basics, functions and objectives of the national education system are stated in Article 4 of Republic of Indonesia Law Number 2 of 1999, namely, National Education aim enlighten life nation And develop man Indonesia completely, that is man Which believe And devout to God is Almighty and has noble character, has knowledge and Skills, health physical And spiritual, personality Which Excellent And independent as well as flavor not quite enough answer society And nationality.

Besides That system learning Which during This used is system conventional learning (university coaching), with an instructional atmosphere and is considered not in accordance with the dynamics of scientific development And technology which is fast. Whereas, Indonesia at the moment This is entering era information technology, which occurs with the many information media, disseminators information that is increasingly widespread and instantaneous, as well as information in various forms form Which changed quickly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on results observation Which done researcher in vocational school Country 2 Sidrap that part teachers still use conventional methods And still use books in the learning process, which makes a lot students pay less attention to existing subject matter because of the material Indonesian language packaged not enough draw attention student.

Media has influenced many aspects of life, especially in world education We although with method different, by Because That various kinds of learning media were created to make things easier for teachers and participant educate in process Study teach, with appearance media learning that requires adequate facilities and therefore, created something media learning Which called with Google _ Classroom .When We do learning in a way on line naturally We requires media as a means for learning. Therefore various Platform used as media learning by school And Also University (Agus Salim et al., 2021).

In the initial stages in 2014-2016 the development of Google Classroom was not intended for everyone, only schools that collaborate with google ,

However in month March 2017, google classroom can accessed by part person with use google personal. google classroom is room class structured in process learning Which There is moment Here, Google Classroom can be downloaded on students' cellphones for free, The learning process through Google Classroom is very easy to do, such as Giving assignments also saves time because the teacher gives assignments without paper.

METHODS

The approach used in this research is quantitative. According to (Sugiyono, 2013) method study quantitative is method scientific because it meets scientific principles, namely concrete, objective, measurable, rational and systematic. To get the results of this research, especially First, it is best to create a design for the research that will be carried out. Design study Which done is design experiment. Following description implementation study This depicted in the table simple following :

Table 1. Description Implementation Study

Kelompok	Perlaku
1 Eksperimen	X
2 Kontrol	Y

Information :

X: Treatment in class experiment with use media google classroom

Y: Not given treatment in the experimental class with using media google classroom.

Variable Study

Internal variables This research consists of 2 variables namely: independent variable (independent variable) and dependent variable (dependent variable). Independent variable Use media google classroom moment process Study teach (X), whereas variable bound Results Study Language Indonesian students (Y). Study This held in vocational school Country 2 Sidrap on end semester the 2022/2023 academic year will be completed in May 2023 for the class XI with use media Google Classroom.

Technique Collection Data

(Sugiyono, 2013) state that population is category For a generalization consisting of things or people that meet criteria studies that have been determined by researchers. The population in this study is all class XI students of SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap. Samples are partial or partial representative of a population studied (Arikunto Suharsimi, 2002). sample is a factor of the number and characteristics possessed by the population the. Based on the opinion above, the sample used in This research is Purposive Cluster Random , which is deep sampling research This is 20% from population Which There is, Because amount population exceed 100 that is 146 student. Means $146 \times 20\% = 29$, So sample Which used in study this much 29 student.

Technique in collection data Which used in study This is:

Documentation

Technique documentation give information about amount student in the classroom XI vocational school Country 2 Sidrap year lesson 2022/2023.

Test

Technique test used For measure results Study eye lesson Language Indonesia For student on class XI vocational school Country 2 Sidrap. On end Learning is carried out by tests whose aim is to see student learning outcomes. Test Which intended the is give question form choice double as many as 30 questions. With this, the test taker is able to answer all of them question with Correct so will obtain mark maximum 100.

In this technique the collected data is analyzed using techniques Descriptive statistics. The steps for analyzing data are test results student used For determine classification mark student. Score converted become value on formula as follows:

$$N = \frac{SP}{SM} \times 100$$

Information :

- N : The score obtained by the student
- SP : Score acquisition
- SM : Score maximum
- 100 : Score Highest

Analysis Formula Mean

For know There is or not influence use media google classroom on Indonesian language learning outcomes for class XI students at SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap, so used formula mean as following:

$$M_x = \frac{\sum f_x}{N_x} \quad M_y = \frac{\sum f_y}{N_y}$$

Information:

- M_x : Mark average group experiment
- $\sum f_x$: Total value of the experimental group
- N_x : Number of experimental group students
- M_y : _ Mark Average group control
- $\sum f_y$: Number of control group values
- N_y : Amount student group control

T-test

The t.test is a type of inferential statistical test used for testing significance in a sample group. Group comparison experiment - control with use formula t. test inferential following :

$$T\text{-test} = \frac{M_x - M_y}{SD_{bm}}$$

Information :

t : Level significant (t count)

M_x : Average value of the experimental group

N_x : Average value of the control group Elementary School *b* : Standard Average deviation

Steps use formula the as following :

- a. Find the squared SD of both groups using the formula:

$$SD^2 x = \frac{\sum fx^2}{N_x} - (M_x)^2$$

$$SD^2 y = \frac{\sum fy^2}{N_y} - (M_y)^2$$

- b. Look for elementary school square average second group with formula :

$$SD^2 M_x = SD^2 M_y = \frac{SD^2 x}{N_x - 1} + \frac{SD^2 y}{N_y - 1}$$

- c. Look for Elementary School *bm* with formula : Elementary School *bm* =

$$\sqrt{SD^2 mx + SD^2 my}$$

Results analysis data Which obtained through formula the used For test hypothesis that filed as following :

- a. If mark acquisition T count big than T table 5%, so Ho _ rejected And H 1 accepted.
- b. If the acquisition value is T, calculate smaller than T table 5%, then H o is accepted and H 1 rejected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Study which is implemented on class XI in State Vocational School 2 Sidrap. Class The sample selected was class XI of SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap. In research This group was divided into 2 groups, namely the experimental group which was in process activity Study will use google classroom And group control which is not used in learning activities Google Classroom. After carrying out the teaching and learning process the two groups were given a lesson test.

Presentation Data

Based on results study Which Already done use documentation And test form choice double as instrument collection data, then obtained results as following :

- a. Data with variable X is data results Study Language Indonesia Which using Google Classroom (group experiment)
- b. Data with variable Y is data results Study Language Indonesia Which No using Google Classroom (group control)

To facilitate the data analysis process, the data will be presented first Which has collected Then analyzed Then next with test hypothesis with technique statistics as following :

Table 2. Score and Value Group Experiment

No	Score	Mark
1	26	87
2	25	83
3	24	80
4	27	90
5	28	93
6	27	90
7	26	87
8	22	73
9	26	87
10	23	77

Source Data : Results Test

Table 3. Score and Value Results Group Control

No	Score	Mark
1	25	83
2	22	73
3	27	90
4	21	70
5	23	77
6	26	87
7	26	87
8	24	80
9	20	67
10	20	67

Source Data : Results Test

Analysis Data

Find out whether using Google Classroom will affect the results learning Indonesian for class XI students at SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap, then the results data Study second group will processed And analyzed in table calculation mean and continued with test t-test as following :

Table 4. Table Work Calculation T-test

Experiment			Control		
fx^2	f	F	X/Y	F	fY
25,947	279	3	93	-	-
16,200	180	2	90	1	90
22,707	261	3	87	2	174
20,667	249	3	83	1	83
6,400		1	80	3	240
11,858	154	2	77	2	154
5,329		1	73	1	73
- 9,800	-	-	70	2	140
- 8,978	-	-	67	2	134
109.108	1,276	15	Σ	14	
1,088	85,292				

Mean of experimental group (x) and control group (y) 1)

$$M_x = \frac{\sum f_x}{N_x} = \frac{1.276}{15} = 85,067$$

$$M_y = \frac{\sum f_y}{N_y} = \frac{1.088}{15} = 77,714$$

Test T-test

1. Find the SD of variable X and variable Y

$$SD^2 x = \frac{\sum fx^2}{N_x} - (M_x)^2$$

$$= \frac{109.100}{15} - (85,067)^2$$

$$= 7,273,87 - 7,236,394$$

$$= 37,466$$

$$SD^2 y = \frac{\sum fy^2}{N_y} - (M_y)^2$$

$$= \frac{85.292}{15} - (77,714)^2$$

$$= 6,092,285 - 6,039,465$$

$$= 52,82$$

2. Find SD 2 M x and SD 2 M y

$$SD^2 M_x = \frac{SD^2 x}{N_x - 1}$$

$$= \frac{37,466}{15 - 1} = \frac{37,466}{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2,676 \\
 SD^2 M_y &= \frac{SD^2 y}{N_y - 1} \\
 &= \frac{52,82}{15 - 1} = \frac{52,82}{14} \\
 &= 4,063
 \end{aligned}$$

3. Looking for elementary school $_{bm}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Elementary School }_{bm} &= \sqrt{SD^2_{mx} + SD^2_{my}} \\
 &= \sqrt{2,676 + 4,063} \\
 &= \sqrt{6,739} \\
 &= 2,595
 \end{aligned}$$

4. Look for mark t-test :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{t-test} &= \frac{M_x - M_y}{\frac{SD_{bm}}{\sqrt{db}}} \\
 &= \frac{85,067 - 77,714}{\frac{2,595}{\sqrt{27}}} = \frac{7,353}{0,505} \\
 &= 14,56
 \end{aligned}$$

$$t = 2,833$$

$$db = (N_x - 1) + (N_y - 1)$$

$$= (15 - 1) + (14 - 1)$$

$$= 14 + 13$$

$$= 27$$

$$T \text{ table } 5\% = 2,052$$

DISCUSSION

This research was conducted with the aim of finding out the existence of an influence Google Classroom based learning media on eye learning outcomes Indonesian language lesson for class XI SMK Negeri 2 Sidrap. Implementation location study This is at in vocational school Country 2 Sidrap with take sample as many as 29 students. In determining the division of experimental groups and control that is chosen in a way random on each room class.

Based on acquisition mark Which obtained on study This show difference results Study Language Indonesia student class XI vocational school Negeri 2 Sidrap which uses Google Classroom in the learning process is more better than students who carry out the learning process as usual. Results Learning can be seen from the comparison of test results that have been carried out on student at the end learning process.

Results from the experimental group using Google Classroom on process Study obtain mark Which more tall compared to with control group who did not use Google Classroom during the process Study. Matter the can seen from results acquisition analysis data Which done show mark average group experiment ($M_x = 85,067$) while the control group ($M_y = 77,714$). This value shows that mark M_x more big compared to M_y ($85,067 > 77,714$) And on test t. test get T count $2,833 >$ from T table 5% (2.052) with db 27.

Based on acquisition Which obtained on statement in on that hypothesis which states that there is an influence on the use of Google Classroom media on Indonesian language learning outcomes class XI student at SMK Negeri 2

Sidrap "accepted" . Consequence reception the, so hypothesis Which stated that there was no influence on the use of Google Classroom media results Study Language Indonesia student class XI vocational school Country 2 Sidrap was "rejected" .

Thus it can be concluded that the use of Google media The classroom in the learning process can have a positive influence. This matter prove with use media google classroom in process learning provides quite satisfactory student learning outcomes in comparison No using Google Classroom media on process Study.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on results from study about influence use media Google Classroom on Indonesian language learning outcomes for class XI vocational school students Country 2 Sidrap can concluded as following Based on results research, accordingly with testing hypothesis through analysis data Which obtained from results learning group control more low compared the learning results of the experimental group were $M_x=85.067 > M_y=77.714$. Difference from results Which obtained show exists influence use media Google Classroom on the results of class XI Indonesian language learning at SMK Negeri 2 Sidenreng rappang. Based on results study can concluded that hypothesis Which state exists influence use media google classroom to results Study Language Indonesia class XI vocational school Country 2 Sidenreng rappang for the 2022/2023 academic year is accepted. Analysis results with tests end show that student Which taught use media google classroom impact very positive And satisfying results Study student compared to with Which taught without use media google classroom .For Students are expected to provide benefits, namely being able to play an active role in learning activities using Google Classroom. With Being involved and active in the learning process will certainly improve learning outcomes student.

For Teacher

Use media learning No free from role Teacher in carry out activity learning so that Teacher as facilitator And motivator in learning. Because all potency which exists in students No can appear suddenly without There is encouragement from Teacher.

For School

Study This expected give description about development Media tools help in the learning process for teachers and researchers so that google classroom This or media other applied in learning.

FURTHER STUDY

Study This made as inspiration in do something activity which is useful in the field of education, especially since this is an initial model in develop

technology as well as make material study For making media learning Which more creative and more Good Again.

REFERENCES

Agussalim, Ferdiansyah, H., Zulkifli, N., & Yakub, R. (2021). Model Use Blended Learning to Results Study in period Pandemic Covid-19 . 5 (2), 329-334.

Aqib, & Zainal. (2014). Models, Media, and Contextual Learning strategies (Innovative). Yrama Widya.

Armida, S., & Fitri. (2022). Influence Utilization Application Google Classroom To Results Study Student in vocational school Kartika 1-2 Padang (Study Eye Lesson Major Automation And System manage Office When Online) . 01 (2), 387-396.

Arsyad, A. (2014). Media Learning . PT. King Grafindo Homeland.

Atikah, R.-, Prihatin, RT, Hernayati, H., & Misbah, J. (2021). Utilization of Google Classroom as a Learning Media During the Covid-19 Pandemic. Journal Pick , 7 (1), 7-18. <https://doi.org/10.31980/jpetik.v7i1.988>

Cahayani, N. L. P., & Sau, Q. S. B. (2022). Influence Use Media Learning Based Application Android And Style Study to Results Studying Economics MA Tawakkal Denpasar Academic Year.... Arthaniti Studies , 3 (1), 20-27. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395507>

Daryanto. (2016). Learning Media . Gava Media.

Ministry of National Education. (2007). Standard Process For Unit Education Base And Intermediate.

Center Bookkeeping Department Education National. Jakarta .

Gagné, M., McGaughey, G.B., & Rappe, A. K. (1998). π -Stacking interactions. Alive and well in proteins. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* , 273 (25), 15458- 15463. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.273.25.15458>

Hamalik, O. (1989). Media Education . Image Aditya.

Hilmi, AW, Setiawan, D., & Farid, MM (2022). Effect of Application Use Google Classroom to Results Study Student Class X in vocational school LAB SCHOOL UNESA. *Journal Education Economy (JUPE)* , 10 (2), 172-177. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jupe.v10n2.p172-177>

Ministry Law And HAM. (2012). Act R.I No. 12/2012 about Education Tall. Law , 18 .

Khair, U. (2018). Learning Language Indonesia And Literature (BASTARDS) in elementary school And MI .2 (1).

Mahardini, m m A. (2020). Analysis situation use google classroom on learning online physics. *Journal of Education Physics*, 8 (2), 215-224.

Sabila, ANA (2022). THE EFFECT OF ROUTINE READING THE QUR'AN ON INTELLIGENCE SPIRITUAL STUDENTS CLASS IX MTs COTTAGE BOARDING SCHOOL MADINATUNNAJAH JOMBANG CIPUTAT . 03 .

Andri, M, Hasanuddin, Hermansyah, Tahir

Sudjana, N. (1989). Approach System for Administrator Education (Draft And Application) .

Sudjana, N. (2015). Process Basics Study Teaching . CV Sinar New.

Wahid, A. (2018). Importance Media Learning In Increase Performance Study .5.

Yanto, A. (2016). Role Playing Method to Improve Learning Outcomes Student On Eye Lesson Social Sciences. Journal Horizon Pendas , I (1), 55–64.
<https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/266425-method-bermain-peran-role-playing-for-3f4b0135.pdf>

Yaumi, Mohammed. 2015. Model Development Media And Technology Learning Something Introduction. Makassar.